

STUDYING THE CAUSES OF FIBROADENOMA DISEASE IN YOUNG GIRLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Relevance. In recent years, breast diseases, in particular various tumors, have had a significant impact on women's health worldwide. Currently, fibroadenoma (breast cancer) is a benign tumor that is common in young women and girls. Since the widespread prevalence of fibroadenoma in young girls is associated with reproductive health, the psychological state of women, and future motherhood opportunities, an in-depth study of the topic is one of the current issues. Based on the results of epidemiological observations conducted in Uzbekistan, approximately 7-9% of young girls aged 18-25 have been diagnosed with fibroadenoma. Objectives of the study: To conduct a metrological analysis of the causes of fibroadenoma in young girls, to identify hormonal and hereditary factors, and to study the factors influencing it.

Research methods and techniques. The research was conducted in the department of mammology at the Tashkent City Oncology Dispensary in 2024-2025. Bunda 15 - 25 yoshdagi 420 nafar qizlarning tanlab olinib 2 guruhga bo'lini: asosiy fibroadenoma kasalligi bor ($n = 210$) qizlarga va nazorat guruhidagi ($n = 210$) sog'lom qizlar. All participants were examined by a mammologist. As a result of clinical examinations: In these patients, a family history of breast diseases in the mother and sister was confirmed. The patients were surveyed about the age of first menstruation, the duration and regularity of the menstrual cycle, sleep disorders, and the presence of chronic endocrinological diseases. Ultrasound examination: determined the size, number and location of fibroadenomas. Hormonal tests: FSH, LH, estradiol, progesterone, prolactin, TSH levels were assessed. Biochemical markers: insulin, glucose were tested.

Results: According to the results of the study, 68% of girls with fibroadenomas had hormonal disorders, mainly increased estrogen and prolactin levels, and decreased progesterone. 22% of girls had a hereditary predisposition (their mother or sisters had fibroadenomas). 10% of cases are due to environmental and lifestyle factors (stress, lack of sleep). The average size of fibroadenoma is 2.3 ± 0.8 cm: 78% < 2 cm (164), 2% > 2 cm (46). The risk of developing fibroadenoma is 1.9 times higher in those with high prolactin levels ($OR=1.9;95\%$). No pathological tumors were found in the mammary glands of the girls in the control group, but signs of mastopathy were detected in 8.6% of girls. So the main reasons for the development of fibroadenoma in young girls are: hormonal imbalance, hereditary predisposition, and lifestyle factors. Increased estrogen levels and progesterone deficiency are the most important pathogenetic mechanisms of fibroadenoma. These results suggest that estrogen/progesterone imbalance may promote fibroepithelial proliferation in the mammary gland.

Conclusion: The results of the study showed that many factors interact in the development of fibroadenoma in young girls. Prolactin and thyroid hormones also increase the risk of fibroadenoma. As a preventive measure, it is recommended to adhere to a healthy lifestyle, reduce stress, and undergo regular mammological examinations.